

Studies on Mustard (*Brassica juncea*) Seeds : Electron Micrography and Protein Characteristics

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Electron micrographs of mustard seeds showed the location and attachment of different components, and higher magnification was required for distinguishing hull from endosperm. The processes of extraction of oil and protein used are suitable for avoiding glucosinolate hydrolysis which produces isothiocyanates. The protein contents of flour and isolate were 65 and 91% respectively. The essential amino acid content of mustard protein is adequate to make the chemical score 100. Minimum point of nitrogen dispersion occurred at around pH 4.0 and 6.0 due to two isoelectric points. NaCl markedly increased the solubility of mustard protein at the isoelectric point. Mustard protein globulin showed two peaks of 1.7S and 14.3S.

Oriental and brown mustard (*Brassica juncea*) are grown in plenty in India and neighbouring countries. In Europe and Canada these oilseeds are grown as winter and summer rapeseed (*B. napus*) and turnip rape (*B. campestris*). Mustard and rapeseed proteins are becoming important in human nutrition¹. Problems involved in the use of mustard protein in nutrition include the presence of glucosinolates, which on enzymic hydrolysis, yield undesirable and even toxic factors such as isothiocyanates, nitriles and oxazolidinethiones², and the relatively high cellulose content of the seeds³. The breeding of new varieties of rapeseed has been only partially successful with regard to reducing the glucosinolate and cellulose content of the meal⁴. A counter-current procedure for the extraction of protein from defatted rapeseed meal gave 94% of meal nitrogen extraction, and protein content of isolates was as high as 98%⁵. The effects of crushing and heat treatment of high glucosinolate rapeseed with infrared, microwave or in a hot air, upon the utilisation of protein and upon antithyroid activity have been reported⁶. It has been observed⁷ that glucosinolate was removed from rapeseed and mustard seed by methanol-ammonia system. There are reports on the extraction of mustard oil from mustard seed with hexane⁸, the interaction of allyl isothiocyanate with mustard protein⁹, the diffusion extraction of glucosinolate from mustard seed¹⁰, the fractionation of rapeseed meal by cyclone process into flour and hull¹¹, and the procedure for extraction of protein from defatted rapeseed meal¹². The nutritional evaluation of oilseed meal and protein isolates using mice revealed the superiority of the glucosinolate-free rapeseed isolate over other protein sources¹³. The rapeseed protein has been shown to be the best protein for the supplementation of human diets because of the presence of high proportion of essential amino acids¹⁴. The functional characteristics of several legume and oilseed proteins which could be effectively

utilised as protein source of various food products, have been reported¹⁵.

The objective of the present study was to make a systematic investigation on the technological advantage of dehulling of mustard seeds for effective utilisation of oil and protein.

Results and Discussion

The dehulling of mustard seeds has been a major problem for protein isolation from the seeds with high nutritive value. Figs. 1(A) and (B) show the components of a mustard seed on a cut-surface. There is a definite distinction between the components of the seed as illustrated in Figs. 1(C) and (D). A difference in appearance is clearly observed when the magnification is changed as shown in Fig. 2(E) and viewed through the cut-surface of other regions of the seed. The hull and endosperm junction at higher magnification is shown in Figs. 2 (F), (G) and (H). Wet and dry procedures were found effective in removing the hull from the endosperm (Fig. 3). During crushing it is important to avoid glucosinolate hydrolysis because the products are readily soluble in the extracted oil causing pungent odor and poisoning of the catalyst used for hydrogenation. The process (Fig. 3) could be a suitable industrial process for extraction of oil and protein free from the undesirable isothiocyanates.

The various constituents of mustard seed were examined to evaluate the process to be undertaken for the isolation of protein. The protein content of mustard seed varies between 28 and 30% (Table 1) and oil content was around 42%. The yields of protein-rich flour and protein isolate were 38 and 16% respectively per 100 g of seeds. The protein content of the prepared 'proteins isolate' was 91% with light brown in colour and that of flour was 65% having brown colour. No significant increase of extracted nitrogen was observed above a meal-solvent ratio of 1 : 10. The protein

Fig. 1. Scanning electron micrograph of different section of a mustard seed (*Brassica juncea*): (A) cut-surface of a seed, (B) cut-surface of a seed from an other angle, (C) part of Fig. (A) at higher magnification and (D) higher magnification of a cut-seed.

showed significantly large amounts of sulphur containing amino acids and lysine content was adequate compared to FAO provisional pattern (Table 2). The chemical score was 100 for mustard protein unlike all other commercially available plant proteins. Comparing the values (Table 2) for sulphur-containing amino acids in mustard seeds, flour and protein, it is apparent that the water-soluble fraction which was discarded during isolate preparation was richer in these amino acids than the precipitated isolate.

The solubility (one percent protein suspension) of mustard protein was highly pH-dependent (Fig. 4). Minimum points of nitrogen dispersion occurred at around pH 4.0 and 6.0 due to its two widely separated isoelectric points. The combined protein isolate showed appreciable solubility at around neutral pH. The solubility profile of mustard protein in NaCl was different at various pH regions. NaCl (0.5 M) markedly increased the

solubility of mustard protein at isoelectric points (Fig. 4). Ultracentrifugation pattern of mustard protein determined using a double-sector interference cell and counter balance showed that the globulin fraction contained two peaks of 1.7S and 14.3S (Fig. 5).

Experimental

Mustard protein isolation: The cleaned seeds were subjected to superheated steam (5 psig) through an exhaustor for 7 min followed by tray-drying at 70° for 8 h. The dried seeds were dehulled and air-classified. The dehulled cotyledons were ground to flour, and oil was extracted with analytical grade hexane (1 : 5) and the solvent removed in air. Hulls and fines were separately extracted for oil and meal.

A 10% (w/v) dispersion of defatted flours was

Fig. 2. Scanning electron micrograph of different sections of a mustard seed (*Brassica juncea*): (E) cut-surface of a seed from an other side, (F) hull and endosperm at higher magnification, (G) part of endosperm of a seed, and (H) hull and endosperm junction of seed.

TABLE 1—PRODUCT YIELD COMPOSITION OF *Brassica juncea* (DRY WT. BASIS)*

Product	Oil %	Hull %	Protein % (Nx 6.25)	Crude fibre %	Ash %	Cc flour	Yield (g/100g seed)
Seeds	42.8	22	29.5	7.2	4.7	Brown	—
Flour	1.8	—	65	3.9	7.2	Brown	38
Protein isolate	0.8	—	91	0.1	1.9	Light brown	16

*Standard deviation is approximately 2%.

TABLE 2—AVERAGE ESSENTIAL AMINO ACID COMPOSITION AND INDICES OF MUSTARD PROTEIN

Amino acid	FAO*	Soybean	Mustard seed	Mustard protein flour	Mustard protein isolate	Standard deviation
Isoleucine	4.0	4.7	4.2	4.3	4.3	0.01
Leucine	7.0	7.3	7.2	7.4	7.2	0.02
Lysine	5.5	6.4	5.8	6.4	6.3	0.02
Methionine + Cysteine	3.5	2.4 ^a	4.9	4.6	4.2	0.03
Phenylalanine + Tyrosine	6.0	8.3	7.1	8.3	7.6	0.02
Threonine	4.0	3.7	4.4	4.7	4.4	0.01
Tryptophan	1.0	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.5	0.01
Valine	5.0	4.9	5.1	5.3	5.2	0.02
Chemical score		68	100	100	100	

*WHO (1973). ^aDenotes first limiting amino acid as determined by chemical analysis.

Fig. 3. Procedure for extraction of oil and protein from *Brassica juncea*.

made in distilled water, adjusted to pH 8.5 with 1*N* NaOH and stirred for 30 min at 40°. The extract was then separated from the insoluble residue by centrifuging (199 G) for 15 min. The extraction procedure was repeated to increase the yield of protein. The pH of the combined extract was adjusted to 4.0 to precipitate the major proteins. The mixture was centrifuged at 1242 G for 10 min and the supernatant was separated from the residue by decantation. The supernatant was stored in the refrigerator at 8° for 30 min and re-centrifuged for further separation of proteins. The pH was again adjusted to 6.0 for further separation of other proteins. The precipitates were separated by centrifugation as above, washed and mixed with proteins collected earlier, neutralised to pH 7.0 and freeze-dried.

Determination of moisture, protein, fat, crude fibre ash and amino acids: Moisture¹⁶ and nitrogen content of mustard protein¹⁷ isolate was determined by standard methods. Fat content was determined after extraction with hexane (A.R.). Crude fibre

Fig. 4. Solubility profile of mustard protein isolates extracted under indicated conditions: (O) distilled water and (□) 0.5 *M* NaCl.

was determined according to the reported method¹⁸. The ash content was determined by heating the sample in a furnace at 600° for 2 h.

Amino acid analysis was conducted on a Beckman 120 C analyser using the two-column procedure¹⁸ after hydrolysis of the sample (25 mg) with 6*N* HCl (7 ml) under vacuum in a sealed ampule for 24 h at 110°.

For ultracentrifugal analysis, the protein isolate was suspended in a buffered salt solution (0.0325 *M* K₂HPO₄, 0.0026 *M* KH₂PO₄ and 0.40 *M* NaCl) at pH 7.6, $\mu=0.5$. Sedimentation velocity measurements were made with a Spinco ultracentrifuge operated at 52000 r.p.m. Sedimentation coefficients were calculated by the reported procedure¹⁹. The solubility studies of protein were made according to the standard methods¹⁹.

The hull and endosperm of mustard seed were studied by electron microscopy. The specimens were examined in a Cambridge Stereoscan 96113 electron microscope at 23 kV.

Fig. 5. Ultracentrifugation pattern of mustard protein isolates.

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